

A data-driven multicriteria decision making tool for classifying investments in energy efficiency

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Abstract

Mainstreaming energy efficiency finance is considered as a key priority. The capability offered by Multicriteria Decision Analysis to integrate cross-domain financial and energy consumption data, combined with statistical analysis, can contribute to build the necessary market confidence in energy efficiency projects and make them an attractive investment asset class. In this context, the aim of this paper is to propose a solid methodological framework in order to support the financing procedure of energy efficiency investments, and to identify improved grand financing plans, considering a series of factors which are of vital importance for the sustainability of such actions and the limitation of investment risk. A decision support tool, developed in Python, is presented which implements the suggested methodology, improving the decision making for the investor in terms of the percentage of grand financing per project. The developed methodology has been applied on a reliable dataset of energy efficiency projects from several cities in Latvia, where the actual performance of the investments is exploited.

Keywords: Decision support; Energy efficiency; Energy management; Investment financing; Multicriteria decision analysis; TOPSIS; Data analytics

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1. Introduction

Current climate change threats and increasing CO₂ emissions, in particular from the building stock, represent a context where it is necessary to act upon and provide efficient manners to manage energy consumption and generation in buildings and contribute to a decarbonised economy [1]. Nearly 97% of the building stock in the European Union (EU) is not considered energy efficient (less than 3% of the building stock in the EU qualifies for an A-label) [2], 75-90% of those standing today will still be in use in 2050, given that the construction rate is overall low [3], with low demolition rates (0.1% per year), low renovation rates (1.2% per year [4]), and an EU building stock inexorably aging [5] with 75% of the actual EU buildings stock built before 1990.

While new buildings can be designed and constructed to be able to produce living spaces with lower energy demand and usage, and while also considering that about 84% of the total building energy [6] is typically consumed during the operational phase (assuming a building life of more than 50 years), the biggest impact on the energy demand can be achieved by improving the energy performance of the existing building stock, through increasing the number and the rate of deep energy renovation and promoting energy management (with expected savings of 60% or more) [7].

Energy efficiency plays a crucial role in achieving the overarching aim of the EU's Green Deal towards "climate-neutrality" by 2050. "Energy Efficiency First" or "Efficiency First" principle can also play a game-changing role in the energy transition [8]. The EU has already stressed the importance of scaling up investments in energy efficiency to avert climate change [9]. More specifically, the European Commission (EC) estimates that to achieve the newly agreed 55% climate target by 2030, around 275 billion of investments per year are needed, most of them in energy efficiency [10].

However, increasing the financial institutions' deployment of capital in energy efficiency investments remains still a challenge [11]. Energy efficiency projects are often fragmented, with high transaction costs, and with no evidence-based platform that would allow investors and financial institutions to assess the risk, the financial performance of the investments, as well as the impact on energy efficiency [12]. Partly due to the heterogeneity of energy efficiency investments and to the immaturity of the market for such investments, the relative costs for project development, finance documentation, processing and aggregation (together "transaction costs") are high, making entry into this business unattractive for many financial institutions [13]. The investment institutions lack the technical understanding of the essence of energy efficiency investments; this often creates a lack of trust in such investments, acting as a barrier to including energy efficiency projects in the investment portfolio, even though they are often robust, with a guaranteed return [14].

Mainstreaming energy efficiency finance is considered as a key priority [15]. The capability offered by Multicriteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) to integrate cross-domain financial and energy consumption, combined with statistical analysis, is the key for building the necessary market confidence in energy efficiency projects and making them an attractive investment asset class. The use of historical data pooled from major market segments can encourage more investments in energy efficiency, de-risking investments [16-17].

In this context, the aim of this paper is to propose a solid methodological framework in order to support the financing procedure of energy efficiency investments, and to identify improved grand financing plans, considering a series of factors which are of vital importance for the sustainability of such actions and the limitation of investment risk. A decision support tool, developed in Python, is presented which implements the

suggested methodology, improving the decision making for the investor in terms of the percentage of grand financing per project. The developed methodology has been applied on reliable dataset of energy efficiency projects from several cities in the country of Latvia, where the actual performance of the investments is exploited.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. In Section 2, the proposed methodological framework and the relevant decision support tool are presented. In section 3, the dataset in which the proposed framework was applied and tested, is described. In Section 4, the results of the experimental application, along with a comparison of the proposed financing plan with the implemented financing plan, are presented. In Section 5, the contributions and conclusions of the current study are discussed, respectively.

2. Methodology

The proposed methodological framework is presented in Figure 1. It aspires to combine existing techniques and methods from the MCDA field with a set of indexes which measure the efficiency of an investment and have been selected based on statistical analysis conducted on the available dataset and in close collaboration with investors.

MCDA belongs to the scientific field of Operational Research (OR), aiming to provide models that are capable of dealing with multivariable optimisation problems, incorporating all different parameters of the problem. The most crucial components of each MCDA problem are the detailed and careful analysis of the optimisation criteria and the proper selection of the MCDA method that will be exploited.

Figure 1. Methodological approach

2.1 The selected evaluation criteria

The adoption of energy efficiency measures is influenced by different categories and types of contextual factors [18]. The proposed methodology is based on four criteria which take into consideration the most crucial parameters of both the building in which the investment is carried out and the investment itself. After studying the available datasets of energy efficiency projects from several cities in the country of Latvia (location, economic sector, building construction year, building functionality, heating area, energy efficiency measures cost, energy consumption (baseline), energy savings (expected / actual), as well as the correlation of a series of factors to the effectiveness of the energy efficiency investment, and in communication with the Decision Makers (DMs) and experts in the field, the most influential indexes which affect the prosperity of such an investment were extracted.

2.1.1 Energy Reduction per Cost

The Energy Reduction per Cost index (KWh/€) is one of the most important factors which should be considered. It indicates the amount of energy savings projected with the investment cost. The Energy Reduction per Cost index is described by the following equation:

$$\text{Energy Reduction per Cost} = \frac{ES}{TC} \quad (1)$$

where ES indicates the actual energy savings achieved and TC the total cost of the investment.

2.1.2 Energy Reduction Percentage per Cost

The Energy Reduction Percentage per Cost (€^{-1}) index indicates the percentage of energy reduction per unit of investment cost. The Energy Reduction Percentage per Cost index is described by the following equation:

$$\text{Energy Reduction Percentage per Cost} = \frac{ES}{EC_{before} \times TC} \quad (2)$$

where EC_{before} indicates the energy consumption of the building before the implementation of the energy efficiency measures, ES the actual energy savings achieved after the implementation of the measures and TC the total cost of the investment.

2.1.3 Building Age

Despite the fact that the abovementioned indexes are of great importance for the evaluation of energy efficiency investments, there are two more factors which can be considered during the comparison of the alternative actions. The first of those factors is related to the building age, which is an important factor for investors. The older buildings usually are less energy efficient, thus, offering opportunities for significant improvements

even with a series of small-scale measures.

2.1.4 *Building Consumption per Heating Area*

Finally, the fourth evaluation metric to be considered is the Building Consumption per Heating Area index (MWh/m²). This metric aims to normalise the consumption per building based on the building's heating area, in order to make the buildings' consumption comparable. Buildings with higher consumption per heating area are capable of achieving greater consumption improvements, constituting better investments opportunities. The Building Consumption per Heating Area index is described by the following equation:

$$\text{Building Consumption per Heating Area} = \frac{EC_{before}}{BHA} \quad (3)$$

where EC_{before} indicates the energy consumption of the building before the implementation of the energy efficiency measures and BHA is an acronym for Building Heating Area.

2.2 *The TOPSIS Method*

Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) is a commonly used MCDA method which belongs to the Multiattribute Utility Theory (MAUT) subfield of multicriteria analysis. It was originally developed in 1982 by Hwang and Yoon [19], but many variations of the method have been developed over the years [20-21], with the most indicative one being found in the development of Fuzzy TOPSIS [22, 23, 24]. TOPSIS, in its various forms, has been widely used for energy efficiency related problems [25-26], as well as to support decision-making in other sectors, such as utilisation of energy sources [27], electricity generation [28-29], environmental assessment [30], energy poverty [31] and transport [32].

In the context of this paper, TOPSIS is utilised in order to provide a descending ranking of the alternatives based on the four criteria which were analysed in section 2.1. The input of the algorithm are the alternatives (n) of the problem, the evaluation criteria (q), the offsets for the evaluation criteria (w_i) and the evaluation matrix which includes the performance (f_{ij}) of each alternative (i) in each criterion (j).

According to Sarmas et al. [33], the steps of the TOPSIS method are described as follows:

- Step 1: Normalised Decision Matrix: The formulation of the normalised decision matrix is a necessary process in order to ensure that data are in the same scale. Given the $n \times q$ decision matrix, the new normalised decision matrix is calculated using the following equation for each element f_{ij} of the initial matrix:

$$r_{ij} = \frac{f_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n f_{kj}^2}} \quad (4)$$

- Step 2: Weighted Normalised Decision Matrix: The relative significance of the model's criteria can be quantified by transforming the normalised decision matrix into the weighted normalised decision matrix. The weighted normalised decision matrix is created by multiplying each element of the normalised decision matrix's column by the offsets, as follows:

$$t_{ij} = r_{ij} \times W_j, \text{ where } W_j = \frac{w_j}{\sum_{k=1}^q w_k} \quad (5)$$

- Step 3: Positive and Negative Ideal Solution: The positive ideal solution A^+ and the negative ideal solution A^- can be computed from the weighted normalised decision matrix with the following formula:

$$A^+ = \langle \{\min(t_{ij}), i = 1, 2, \dots, n | j \in J_-\}, \max(t_{ij}), i = 1, 2, \dots, n | j \in J_+\rangle \quad (6)$$

$$A^- = \langle \{\max(t_{ij}), i = 1, 2, \dots, n | j \in J_-\}, \min(t_{ij}), i = 1, 2, \dots, n | j \in J_+\rangle \quad (7)$$

where J_+ is the subset of maximisation criteria and J_- is the subset of minimisation criteria.

- Step 4: Separation Distance from the Positive and Negative Ideal Solution: Let t_k^+ be the positive ideal value and t_k^- the negative ideal value for criterion k . The separation distance (L^2 - Distance) of each alternative from the positive and the negative ideal value, respectively, are calculated as follows:

$$S_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^q (t_{ik} - t_k^+)^2} \quad (8)$$

$$S_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^q (t_{ik} - t_k^-)^2} \quad (9)$$

- Step 5: Relative Closeness to the Ideal Solution: The relative closeness to the ideal solution can be computed by comparing the separation distance from the ideal and the negative ideal solution. The higher the relative closeness to the ideal solution, the better is the ranking of the alternative. The formula for computing the relative closeness to the ideal solution for alternative i is given by the following equation:

$$C_i = \frac{S_i^-}{S_i^+ + S_i^-} \quad (10)$$

2.3 *Labelling energy efficiency investments*

After the ranking of the TOPSIS method is produced, each alternative has been evaluated with a score and a ranking position. The next step of the proposed framework includes the creation of five distinct classes in order to efficiently label new investments. The aim of the proposed financing plan is to label new investments within the following classes: {Strongly Negative, Negative, Neutral, Positive, Strongly Positive}. The

limitation adjustment between the different classes is conducted according to the TOPSIS method results.

2.3.1 Default Categorisation

The classic approach indicates the equal distribution of alternatives between the five classes. This means that the 20% of the alternatives with the highest ranking should constitute the “Strongly Positive” class, the following 20% of the alternatives should constitute the “Positive” class, etc. Finally, the alternatives with the lowest scores would constitute the “Strongly Negative” class, implying the least favoured actions to invest in. Each time a new energy efficiency action should be evaluated, the respective alternative is given a TOPSIS score and according to this score it is labelled in one of the classes.

2.3.2 Adjusted Categorisation

Any decision support tool should incorporate the DM’s preferences, trying to be as much flexible and configurable as possible. In this respect, an advanced functionality is also developed, enabling the DM to adjust the classes limits making the tool more flexible in any direction (either stricter, or more lenient). Consequently, the number of alternatives per class from the train set can be configured by the user. If, for example, the DM wishes to apply a strict classification, he/she could configure that the “Strong Positive” class must be made of only the top 5% of the alternatives. On the contrary, for a more lenient approach, he/she could adjust the limit of the “Strong Positive” class to 30%, or even reduce the percentage of the alternatives of the “Negative” and “Strong Negative” classes. Finally, this functionality allows the DM to reduce the number of classes. Setting for example the percentage of “Neutral” to zero, then the classes are automatically reduced to four, resulting in a less diverse labelling of the energy efficiency actions.

2.4 *Decision Support Tool and User Interaction*

The proposed methodological framework has been developed in Python 3.0 programming language. Python is a general-purpose, high level language, which is extensively used in the academic field. It provides a series of supplementary libraries which were used for the implementation of the model. More specifically, Pandas open source library was used for importing the dataset as a DataFrame object, NumPy library for scientific computing was used for the statistical analysis of the available data and Matplotlib was exploited for the production of high quality figures and visualizations.

The user interaction with the model has been kept as simple as possible. Firstly, the user should give as input the new investment's parameters. The tool, then, calculates the necessary indexes for the project. Secondly, the user is asked to assign offsets to the four optimisation criteria according to his/her preferences. The TOPSIS method is performed, creating the ranking of the investments and the default boundaries of the five classes, subsequently. Finally, the user has the opportunity to adjust these boundaries, customising the labelling of the investments. The output of the methodology is the label of the candidate energy efficiency investment into one of the five predefined classes.

3. Dataset Analysis

3.1 *Dataset Information*

The validity of the proposed methodological framework was tested in detail within a pool of 312 energy efficiency projects, which were gathered and will be analysed in this section. The utilised dataset was sufficiently pre-processed through data cleaning and analysis, in order to be suitable for the experimental application of the proposed framework. The energy efficiency projects that have been gathered stem from numerous cities in Latvia and have all been partly grant financed from 2009 until 2015.

The most important information that is available on the utilised dataset, which has been used for statistical analysis (correlation, mean values, variance etc.) and for training the proposed model is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Experimental Application Dataset Information

Available Dataset Information
Project City
Economic Sector
Building Construction Year
Building Functionality
Heating Area
Energy Efficiency Measures Cost
Energy consumption (baseline)
Energy savings (actual)

As shown in Table 2, most buildings included in the dataset are used as educational institutions, factories and preschool educational institutions, while the majority of the buildings are placed in Riga, Daugavpils and Rezeknes. 239 of the renovated buildings belong to the public sector, while 73 buildings belong to the private sector. Moreover, it should be highlighted that the most common renovation actions that were performed are: (a) renovation of the building's enclosing structures, (b) heat supply and ventilation system renovation (c) energy efficient lighting and (d) wood chips, biomass pellets and straw boiler house.

Table 2 Dataset Building Functionalities

Building Functionality	Number of Buildings
Educational Institution	160
Factory	60
Preschool Educational Institution	29
Cultural Building	14
Medical Institution	12
Other functionalities	37

3.2 *Statistical Analysis*

The key attributes of the dataset which were used for training the model are the consumption of the building before and after the renovation actions, as well as the heating area of the buildings and the investment cost. Figure 2 visualises the age of the dataset's building. 50% of the buildings were constructed during either between 1970 and 1980, or between 1980 and 1990, resulting in having old heat supply mechanisms and enclosing structures. This applies in a greater extent for even older buildings which would certainly provide bigger energy reduction in case that they could be financed.

Figure 2. Number of buildings per decade

Figure 3 shows the energy reduction and the investment cost of the buildings that are integrated in the experimental application of the model. The most valuable actions to invest in are placed in the lower right part of the figure, meaning that they result in high energy reduction while maintaining their cost at low levels.

We can note that there are investments with high cost which result in less than half of the energy reduction of other lower cost investments. Therefore, the need for an advanced methodology for financing energy efficiency actions is necessary.

Figure 3 Energy reduction per investment cost

Figure 4 visualises the energy consumption per heating area for the available buildings that we studied. The conclusion from this insight is that the majority of buildings keep this ratio in the range of 0.1-0.3. For buildings that the ratio lies above 0.3, this can be interpreted as excessive energy consumption, indicating that energy efficiency actions would be highly recommended.

Figure 4 Classification of investment according to building consumption per heating area

Finally, before presenting the results of the empirical testing of the methodology, in Table 3 some basic statistics of the four evaluation criteria which are utilised, are presented. The index with the highest variance relatively to its mean value is the energy reduction percentage per cost, while, on the other hand, the least varying one is the building consumption per heating, as expected according to Figure 4. The fourth column of Table 5 can be thought as the negative ideal solution for TOPSIS method before normalisation, because all four criteria are maximisation criteria, meaning that greater values are more preferable. The fifth column can be thought as the positive ideal solution, respectively. An investment that would ideally take these values for all four criteria would achieve the maximum score in TOPSIS ranking.

Table 3 Statistical indexes of the dataset

Index	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Energy Reduction per Cost (KWh/€)	0.913	0.491	0.085	3.686

Index	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Energy Reduction Percentage per Cost ($10^{-6} \times \text{€}^{-1}$)	2.147	1.744	0.131	13.67
Building Age (Years)	49.349	22.379	7	205
Building Consumption per Heating Area (MWh/m ²).	0.24	0.097	0.099	0.851

4. Experimental Results

4.1 Empirical Testing of the Proposed Methodology

For the experimental application of the proposed model we split the dataset into training set and test set, keeping 90% of the buildings as training set. Therefore, 280 buildings were used in order to train the model and extract the five classes, while 32 buildings were inserted to the model as test data and were labelled by the proposed algorithm.

In Table 4, we present the five classes which were created after running the model with the available training set using the default categorisation (each class should include equal number of investments). The offsets for the four criteria were assigned using the Simos method which is considered as an effective tool to assess the criteria importance weights in the field of multicriteria decision aid [34]. Therefore, in communication with the DM, the Energy Reduction per Cost and Energy Reduction Percentage per Cost indexes were considered the most important criteria and thus were assigned 40% weighting factor each, whereas Building Age and Building Consumption per Heating Area indexes were assigned 20% weighting factor each.

As mentioned above, the proposed methodological framework aspires to develop as a dynamic process, as more and more investments are assessed. In this respect, every time a new investment is labelled by the model, then it directly becomes part of the training set making the classes dynamically adjust based on new available data. The third column of Table 4 reflects the five investment classes after all 32 investments of the test set have been evaluated. The dynamic character of the proposed model is reflected by the fact the border for the “Strong Positive” class has decreased from 26.98% to 25.40% after the assessment of the test set investments, indicating that the assessed investments were not so worthy to invest, thus partly dropping the standards for future projects which will be evaluated.

Finally, in the last column a Grand Financing Plan (GFP) is proposed. According to the proposed scheme, the investments of the “Strongly Positive” class should be financed with 90% of their total cost, the investments of the “Positive” class should be financed with 70% of their total cost etc. It is obvious that the proposed financing scheme could be adjusted according to the preferences of the DM, as well as other restrictions that may be introduced such as the available budget.

Table 4 Investment Classes based on the training and the whole dataset

Class	TOPSIS Score (only training set)	TOPSIS Score (whole dataset)	Proposed Grand Financing (%)
Strongly Negative	[0 – 13.02]	[0 – 12.32]	10
Negative	[13.03 – 16.85]	[12.33 – 15.98]	30
Neutral	[16.86 – 20.65]	[15.99 – 19.83]	50
Positive	[20.66 – 26.97]	[19.84 - 25.39]	70
Strongly Positive	[26.98 – 100]	[25.40 – 100]	90

4.2 Comparison of the Proposed and the Implemented Financing Plan

The dataset that was used for the experimental application consists of a portfolio of investments which have already been Grand Financed from 2009 until 2015. The purpose of this section is to compare the already implemented grand financing plan with the proposed plan which stems from the methodological framework.

Figure 5 shows the energy reduction per cost index (KWh/€), which is a key metric of an investment's efficiency, against the grand financing ratio for a subset of the implemented actions. It is clear that several projects which have relatively low investment efficiency have been grand financed with more than 60% (grand financing ratio greater than 0.6), while other projects with high impact in terms of energy efficiency have received significantly less financing.

Another important insight stemming from Figure 4 is that investments with high energy reduction percentage per cost may also be underfinanced.

Figure 5 Grand Financing Ratio vs Investment Efficiency

For example, the yellow dot in the center of the Figure implies an energy

efficiency action with high investment efficiency (the respective index has a value greater than 10), which has received financing with ratio below 0.5. On the other hand, there are multiple inefficient investments which have been overfinanced.

Figure 6 visualises the implemented financial ratio against the TOPSIS score that was generated from the model, for both the implemented grand financing plan (left figure) and the proposed financing plan according to the proposed algorithm (right figure). The left figure shows that although there are several energy efficiency projects which were rightfully financed, there are many investments with low score which could have received lower financing, if any. The right figure shows the implementation of the proposed plan, where, as expected, financing is distributed according to the investment’s label. Consequently, the investments with the lowest cost have been labelled as “Strongly Negative” and they should be financed with the lowest ratio.

Figure 6 Comparison between implemented and proposed financing plan vs TOPSIS score

Finally, we attempt to compare the two grand financing plans in terms of investment efficiency. Such a comparison would be meaningful if energy saving due to financing was calculated. For example, an investment with energy saving of 10 MWh which was received 30% financing, provides 3 MWh energy saving due to financing. The

insights of this comparison are depicted in Table 5.

We can identify that the total budget in the case of the implemented financing plan is more than 15% higher compared to the proposed financing plan, while on the other hand the energy saving difference is insignificant. This leads to the fruitful insight that the proposed plan results in about 1.1 KWh/€, while the implemented one offers only 0.9 KWh/€. Last but not least, this difference would be even higher, if we had assigned even bigger weights in the Energy Reduction per Cost Index.

Table 5 Comparison of implemented and proposed action plans in terms of budget and energy saving

	Implemented Financing Plan	Proposed Financing Plan
Total Budget (€)	59,435,964.78	48,834,203.21
Energy Saving due to Financing (MWh)	53906.5	53275
Energy Saving due to Financing per Total Budget (KWh/€)	0.907	1.091

5. Conclusions

In this paper, an integrated methodological framework for assessing and labelling energy efficiency investments was presented, based on a series of criteria stemming from indexes such as the investment cost and the energy saving achieved, among others. Thus, we define investments that have an extremely strong capacity to meet their energy saving targets, already from their conceptual phase, when they are still considered as project fiches, from the funding institutes.

The overall approach can reduce the uncertainty linked to energy efficiency investments, which can be attributed to the lack of relevant skills and inability to properly

assess investments through a multicriteria environment.

The outcome of this paper aspires to strengthen debt and equity financing of energy efficiency projects, providing investors, financiers and project developers the opportunity to evaluate key performance indicators directly and easily for projects and to label the candidate investments.

In future work, the focus should be on creating even more specialised and sophisticated benchmarks per country, investment type and sector, in order to achieve a more precise and detailed comparison between the alternative actions and make possible to rate project fiches by individual performance indicators or in an aggregated manner. Finally, the constantly increasing momentum of machine learning algorithms can generate useful information and indicators to the investors for energy efficiency financing.

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